

There are divergent opinions regarding the observed differences in K and ϵ_c , the current view, held by most investigators^{2,4}, is the deviation from Beer's law by the complex. Assuming that ϵ_c varies as some function of the concentration of the excess component, usually the donor, Foster et al^{2,4} has shown that a small difference in the extinction coefficient of a complex in a pure solvent and in the same solvent but containing sufficient concentrations of D (or A) can account for the observed differences in the calculated values of K and ϵ_c , although the product $K\epsilon_c$ is constant. The same authors (loc.cit) have shown that minimum deviation from Beer's law for a given measurable concentration of 1:1 complex would occur only when the total solute concentration is minimum, i.e., under the condition $[D]=[A]$. According to Person^{2,6} a better value of the formation constant can be obtained when the concentration of the complex is of the same order of magnitude as that of the most dilute component. It can be shown by simple calculation that keeping the total solute concentration a minimum a larger concentration of the complex with 1:1 stoichiometry can be obtained under equimolar condition than under non-equimolar situation. All these can, therefore, explain the observed differences in the values of K and ϵ_c obtained by equi- and non-equimolar methods. The product $K\epsilon_c$, however, shows a fair constancy in the magnitudes at any particular wavelength, as shown in Table I.

Work on molecular complex formation reaction between PA and a series of substituted benzenes and several condensed benzenes is in progress.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. S. K. Siddhanta for providing laboratory facilities and to the University of Burdwan for granting a scholarship to one of them, Sree Harideb Sil.

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Ag(I), Pb(II) and Zn(II) Complexes of Penicillin-V

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Manuscript received 2 January 1979, accepted 12 March 1979

IN continuation of the studies from these laboratories on the chelation reactions of Penicillins¹⁻³ the present communication reports the study of Ag(I), Pb(II) and Zn(II) complexes of Penicillin-V.

Experimental and Results

All the reagents employed were of high purity. The preparation and standardisation of the metal and the ligand solutions and other experimental details remaining the same as given in the earlier communication³.

Stoichiometry of the complexes formed was ascertained by potentiometric (pH) and conductometric studies. The Bjerrum-Calvin⁴ pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving-Rossotti⁵ was followed to determine various formation constants. For

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potentiometric titrations, the following mixtures keeping acetone : water ratio (v/v) 1 : 1 in 50 ml of the reaction solution, were titrated against carbonate free 0.2 M KOH :

- (A) 5 ml of 0.04 M HClO₄
 (B) Mixture (A) + 10 ml of 0.02M ligand solution (Penicillin-v)
 (C) Mixture (B) + 5 ml of 0.002M metal solution.

The ionic strength of the above solutions was maintained to 0.1 M by adding the required quantity of 1.0 M NaClO₄ solution. Correction for pH-measurements in 50% acetone-water system was done as described by Van-Uitert and Hass⁶ and Irving-Rossotti⁵.

On progressive addition of the alkali during the pH-titrations a precipitate was obtained in each case. The pH of precipitation in different systems being : ~4.25 with Ag(I), ~5.8 with Zn(II) and ~5.0 with Pb(II). Therefore, in these cases all the calculations have been done below the pH of precipitations. Further, with the use of very dilute solution (1 × 10⁻⁴ M) of the metals, possibility of the formation of polynuclear complexes may be ruled out.

Irving and Rossotti⁵ equations were utilised to calculate the values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL^- . The values of log K₁, log K₂ and log β₂ were recorded directly from the formation curves (\bar{n} vs pL^-) and refined by the best least square fits (Table 1).

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS, PV-COMPLEXES

μ = 0.1 (NaClO₄) ; a = Half \bar{n} method ; b = Least Square method

Temp. °C	Method	Ag(I)		Zn(II)		Pb(II)		
		log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
20°	a	4.79	4.87	4.45	9.32	4.88	4.55	9.43
	b	4.78	4.92	4.45	9.37	5.02	4.54	9.56
30°	a	4.52	4.55	4.25	8.80	4.60	4.32	8.92
	b	4.42	4.60	4.28	8.88	4.68	4.28	8.96
40°	a	4.16	4.24	3.93	8.17	4.32	4.03	8.33
	b	4.21	4.26	3.70	8.14	4.37	3.90	8.36

The conductometric and potentiometric (pH) titrations and the values of \bar{n} (≈ 2) confirmed the formation of ML and ML₂ complexes—with Pb(II) and Zn(II), and only 1 : 1 (M : L) complex with Ag(I). (The maximum value of \bar{n} = ≈ 1 in this case.)

A perusal of Table 1 clearly indicates that the order of stability varies as : Ag(I) < Zn(II) < Pb(II). The electronic configurations of Ag(I), Zn(II) and Pb(II) being 4d¹⁰, 3d¹⁰ and 5d¹⁰, 6s² respectively. The greater stability of Zn²⁺ (3d¹⁰) complexes over that of Ag⁺ (4d¹⁰) may be expected in the light of the greater ionic charge and the smaller radius (i.e., the higher values of e²/r ratio) of Zn²⁺. The order of

stability for Zn(II) and Pb(II) complexes, on the basis of electronegativity, ionic size and ionisation potentials, should have been Zn(II) > Pb(II), but the order obtained in this investigation is reverse, i.e., Pb(II) > Zn(II). This seems, probably, due to 52 unit greater nuclear charges in Pb over Zn, which result in the higher values of e²/r ratio for Pb—giving greater stability to its complexes.

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Ceric-Benzilic Acid System as Redox Initiator in the Aqueous Polymerization of Methylmethacrylate

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Manuscript received 31 March 1978, revised 24 October 1978, accepted 12 March 1979

THE use of ceric salts in combination with various organic reducing agents such as alcohols, aldehydes, acids and amines as redox initiators for vinyl polymerization has received much attention recently¹⁻⁴. It was thought that the use of an α-hydroxy acid with ceric salts will be an efficient initiator system. Some preliminary observations made with ceric sulphate-benzilic acid redox system in the aqueous polymerization of methylmethacrylate (MMA) are recorded in the present communication.

Experimental

All the reagents employed were of analytical grade. The polymerization experiments were carried out in the dark at ambient temperature under deaerated conditions (under nitrogen) and at a fixed acid concentration. Polymerization rate (R_p) was followed gravimetrically and degree of polymerization (\bar{P}_n) was measured viscometrically⁵. Palit's dye tests⁶ were applied for the detection of polymer endgroups.